

Earth's Future

Supplementary Information for

Working landscapes under climate change need to be green, moist and cool - a case study of Germany

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Introduction

This Supplementary Information compiles the datasets, diagnostics, and full statistical details supporting the manuscript. Figures include a Spearman correlation matrix among LST, LAI, NDWI, precipitation, NDVI, and canopy height (Fig. S1); trends in late-summer greenness (NDVI_{sep}; September 2018–2024) by land-cover type (Fig. S2); hot-day LST (≥ 40 °C) by land-cover classes (Fig. S3); and LST time series across Germany's thermal landscapes (Fig. S4). Tables document data sources and resolutions (Table S1), model specifications for all linear mixed-effects analyses (Table S2), annual counts of hot days (Table S3), and mean hot-day LST for thermal landscapes and federal states (Tables S4–S5). Complete model outputs relate LST to NDVI_{sep}, canopy height, precipitation, altitude, year, and thermal landscape with land-type random effects, and precipitation to NDVI_{sep}, altitude, LST, year, and thermal landscape (Tables S6–S9). Together, these materials support the main results and ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Supplementary Materials

Fig. S1. Spearman rank-correlation matrix (ρ) among Land Surface Temperature (LST), Leaf Area Index (LAI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), precipitation, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and canopy height.

Fig. S2: Late summer greenness of vegetation ($NDVI_{sep}$) trends by land cover type (time series). $NDVI_{sep}$ represents values for September from 2018 to 2024, based on MODIS.

Fig. S3. Mean land surface temperature (LST) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) on hot days by land cover class a) Forest and agricultural land types and b) Urban land types in Germany (2018–2024). The time series displays average LST on hot days (defined as days with $\geq 40^{\circ}\text{C}$ in at least one pixel) across different CORINE 2018 land cover classes.

Fig. S4. Time series of mean land surface temperature (LST) for different thermal landscapes on *hot days* (2018–2024) across different land-use types in Germany. *Hot days* defined as days with ≥ 40 °C in at least one pixel) across different CORINE 2018 land cover classes.

Table S1: Datasets used for the analysis.

Dataset	Source	Resolution	Temporal Coverage
Land surface temperature (LST)	Landsat 8 & 9 (USGS, 2024)	30 m (16-day interval)	2018–2024 (pixels > 40 °C)
Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	MODIS MOD13Q1 (NASA, 2021)	250 m (16-day interval)	2018–2024 (September only)
Annual Precipitation	German Weather Service <u>DWD Gridded Model</u> (DWD, 2024)	1 km × 1 km	2018–2024 (Annual sum)
Canopy Height	Sentinel-2 (Lang et al., 2023)	10 m	Static (Year 2020)
Altitude	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (NASA, 2013)	30m	Static (Year 2019)
Land Type Classification	CORINE Land Cover (EEA, 2018)	100 m	Static (Year 2018)

Table S2. Equations for Linear Mixed-Effects Models Used in Statistical Analysis

This table presents the model equations used to examine the relationships between land surface temperature (LST) during hot days (defined as days when the maximum LST reached or exceeded 40°C in any pixel in Germany), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI_{sep}), canopy height, annual precipitation, and altitude. The models include fixed effects (NDVI_{sep}, canopy height, precipitation, altitude, and year) and random effects (land cover type) to capture spatial variability across different land categories

Model	Equation
i)	$LST \sim NDVI_{sep} + \text{Canopy Height} + \text{Precipitation} + \text{Altitude} + \text{Year} + (1 \text{Land Type})$
ii)	$\text{Precipitation} \sim NDVI_{sep} + \text{Altitude} + LST + \text{Year} + (1 \text{Land Type})$
iii)	$LST \sim NDVI_{sep} + \text{Year} + \text{Thermal Landscape} + (1 \text{Land Type})$

iv)	Precipitation ~ NDVI _{sep} + Year + Thermal Landscape + (1 Land Type)
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Table S3. Number of hot days per year. *Hot days*, defined as days on which at least one pixel in Germany reached or exceeded 40 °C—derived from cloud-filtered Landsat 8 and 9 imagery at 30 m resolution.

Year	Number of hot days
2018	70
2019	54
2020	37
2021	25
2022	62
2023	49
2024	44

Table S4. Mean hot-day land surface temperature (LST) of prominent thermal landscapes of Germany (2018-2024). *Hot days*, defined as days on which at least one pixel in Germany reached or exceeded 40 °C—derived from cloud-filtered Landsat 8 and 9 imagery at 30 m resolution.

S.n.	Landscape	Mean LST
1	Bodensee	23.7
2	Alpen	24.2
3	Bayerischer Wald	24.8
4	Erzgebirge	24.9
5	Solling-Reinhardswald	25
6	Oberallgäu	25.2
7	Hohes Venn-Rureifel	25.8
8	Thüringer Wald	25.9
9	Müritz-Schorfheide	26.1
10	Harz	26.3
11	Pfälzerwald	26.5

12	Schwarzwald	26.6
13	Soonwald-Taunus	26.7
14	Lüneburger Südheide	27.2
15	Hochsauerland	27.4
16	Odenwald-Spessart	27.7
17	Untere Oder	27.9
18	Nordfriesland	29.6
19	Warnow-Vorpommern	29.9
20	Uckermark	30.2
21	Prignitz	30.3
22	Mittelfranken	30.6
23	Emsland-Oldenburg- Hannover	30.7
24	Breisgau	30.7
25	Altmark-Leipzig- Thüringer Basin	30.9
26	Oderbruch	31
27	Teltow-Berlin-Barnim	31.2
28	Köln-Niederrhein- Münsterland	31.2
29	Stuttgart-Nordbaden	31.6
30	München	31.9
31	Maifeld-Neuwieder Becken	32.1
32	Vorderpfalz-Rhein- Main	32.8

Table S5. Mean hot days land surface temperature (LST) of Federal states of Germany (2018-2024). *Hot days*, defined as days on which at least one pixel in Germany reached or exceeded 40 °C—derived from cloud-filtered Landsat 8 and 9 imagery at 30 m resolution.

S.n.	State	Mean LST
1	Bayern	29.1
2	Mecklenburg- Vorpommern	29.2
3	Saarland	29.4
4	Schleswig-Holstein	29.4
5	Rheinland-Pfalz	29.5
6	Niedersachsen	29.6

7	Sachsen	29.7
8	Brandenburg	29.8
9	Hessen	29.8
10	Baden-Württemberg	30
11	Thüringen	30
12	Hamburg	30.2
13	Nordrhein-Westfalen	30.2
14	Bremen	30.8
15	Berlin	30.9
16	Sachsen-Anhalt	31.2

Table S6. $LST \sim NDVI_{sep} + \text{Canopy Height} + \text{Precipitation} + \text{Altitude} + \text{Year} + (1|\text{Land Type})$

Linear mixed-effects model for land surface temperature (LST) with fixed effects for $NDVI_{sep}$, canopy height, precipitation, altitude, and year, and a random intercept for land type. A hot-day was defined as one where the maximum LST reached or exceeded 40°C in any pixel in Germany.

	LST for hot days		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	34.52	33.67 – 35.38	<0.001
$NDVI_{sep}$	-1.97	-1.98 – -1.96	<0.001
Canopy Height	-0.14	-0.14 – -0.14	<0.001
Precipitation	-0.00	-0.00 – -0.00	<0.001
Altitude	-0.00	-0.00 – -0.00	<0.001
Year [2019]	0.72	0.71 – 0.72	<0.001
Year [2020]	-1.51	-1.51 – -1.50	<0.001

Year [2021]	-3.05	-3.06 – -3.05	< 0.001
Year [2022]	-0.15	-0.16 – -0.15	< 0.001
Year [2023]	-1.04	-1.05 – -1.04	< 0.001
Year [2024]	-1.06	-1.06 – -1.05	< 0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	7.53		
$\tau_{00 \text{ Land_Type}}$	1.53		
ICC	0.17		
$N_{\text{Land_Type}}$	8		
Observations	13946809		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.331 / 0.444		

Table S7. Precipitation \sim NDVI_{sep} + Altitude + LST + Year + (1|Land Type)

Linear mixed-effects model for precipitation with fixed effects for NDVI_{sep}, altitude, LST, and year and a random intercept for land type.

	Precipitation		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	360.36	336.46 – 384.27	< 0.001
NDVI _{sep}	296.89	296.21 – 297.57	< 0.001

Altitude	0.58	0.58 – 0.58	< 0.001
LST	-4.05	-4.08 – -4.02	< 0.001
Year [2019]	138.54	138.22 – 138.87	< 0.001
Year [2020]	102.24	101.92 – 102.57	< 0.001
Year [2021]	172.39	172.04 – 172.73	< 0.001
Year [2022]	70.54	70.21 – 70.86	< 0.001
Year [2023]	337.48	337.14 – 337.81	< 0.001
Year [2024]	290.04	289.71 – 290.36	< 0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	27294.74		
τ_{00} Land_Type	1187.30		
ICC	0.04		
$N_{\text{Land_Type}}$	8		
Observations	13946809		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.589 / 0.607		

Table S8. $LST \sim NDVI_{\text{sep}} + \text{Year} + \text{Thermal Landscape} + (1|\text{Land Type})$

Linear mixed-effects model for LST, with fixed effects for $NDVI_{\text{sep}}$, year, and Thermal Landscape, and a random intercept for land type. A hot-day was defined as one where the maximum LST reached or exceeded 40°C in any pixel in Germany.

	LST for hot days		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	30.40	28.47 – 32.32	<0.001
NDVI _{sep}	-4.05	-4.07 – -4.03	<0.001
Year [2019]	0.60	0.59 – 0.61	<0.001
Year [2020]	-1.67	-1.68 – -1.66	<0.001
Year [2021]	-3.55	-3.56 – -3.54	<0.001
Year [2022]	-0.22	-0.23 – -0.21	<0.001
Year [2023]	-1.38	-1.39 – -1.37	<0.001
Year [2024]	-1.57	-1.58 – -1.56	<0.001
Altmark-Leipzig-Thüringer-Becken	3.19	3.17 – 3.21	<0.001
Bayerischer Wald	-0.21	-0.24 – -0.18	<0.001
Bodensee	2.40	2.23 – 2.57	<0.001
Breisgau	3.57	3.54 – 3.59	<0.001
Emsland-Oldenburg-Hannover	3.31	3.29 – 3.33	<0.001
Erzgebirge	-0.23	-0.26 – -0.20	<0.001

Harz	1.25	1.22 – 1.27	<0.001
Hochsauerland	1.77	1.75 – 1.80	<0.001
Hohes Venn-Rureifel	0.60	0.56 – 0.64	<0.001
Köln-Niederrhein-Münsterland	3.20	3.18 – 3.22	<0.001
Lüneburger Südheide	2.24	2.20 – 2.27	<0.001
Maifeld-Neuwieder becken	3.83	3.78 – 3.87	<0.001
Mittelfranken	3.46	3.44 – 3.48	<0.001
München	3.65	3.60 – 3.71	<0.001
Müritz-Schorfheide	1.31	1.29 – 1.34	<0.001
Nordfriesland	2.21	2.18 – 2.24	<0.001
Oberallgäu	0.22	0.18 – 0.25	<0.001
Odenwald-Spessart	2.47	2.44 – 2.49	<0.001
Oderbruch	3.21	3.18 – 3.24	<0.001
Pfälzerwald	2.02	1.99 – 2.05	<0.001
Prignitz	2.88	2.86 – 2.91	<0.001
Schwarzwald	1.67	1.65 – 1.69	<0.001

Solling-Reinhardswald	0.47	0.43 – 0.51	<0.001
Soonwald-Taunus	1.90	1.86 – 1.95	<0.001
Stuttgart-Nordbaden	4.29	4.27 – 4.31	<0.001
Teltow-Berlin-Barnim	3.36	3.33 – 3.39	<0.001
Thüringer Wald	0.96	0.93 – 0.99	<0.001
Uckermark	2.23	2.20 – 2.26	<0.001
Untere Oder	1.92	1.88 – 1.96	<0.001
Vorderpfalz-Rhein-Main	4.77	4.75 – 4.79	<0.001
Warnow-Vorpommern	2.23	2.21 – 2.25	<0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	7.98		
$\tau_{00 \text{ Land_Type}}$	2.89		
ICC	0.27		
$N_{\text{Land_Type}}$	3		
Observations	5340987		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.271 / 0.465		

Table S9. Precipitation ~ NDVI_{sep} + Year + Thermal Landscape + (1 | Land Type)

Linear mixed-effects model for precipitation with fixed effects for NDVI_{sep}, year, and Thermal Landscape, and a random intercept for land type.

	Precipitation		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	1635.24	1621.81 – 1648.67	<0.001
NDVI _{sep}	55.95	55.22 – 56.69	<0.001
LST	-4.05	-4.09 – -4.02	<0.001
Year [2019]	153.89	153.52 – 154.26	<0.001
Year [2020]	108.20	107.82 – 108.57	<0.001
Year [2021]	197.14	196.74 – 197.54	<0.001
Year [2022]	69.77	69.40 – 70.14	<0.001
Year [2023]	367.48	367.10 – 367.87	<0.001
Year [2024]	290.02	289.65 – 290.40	<0.001
Altmark-Leipzig-Thüringer-Becken	-1175.53	-1176.32 – - 1174.74	<0.001
Bayerischer Wald	-597.87	-598.96 – -596.77	<0.001
Bodensee	-879.13	-886.16 – -872.10	<0.001
Breisgau	-856.36	-857.43 – -855.30	<0.001
Emsland-Oldenburg-Hannover	-982.65	-983.47 – -981.83	<0.001

Erzgebirge	-869.36	-870.60 – -868.12	<0.001
Harz	-868.01	-869.04 – -866.98	<0.001
Hochsauerland	-661.85	-662.87 – -660.83	<0.001
HohesVenn-Rureifel	-783.78	-785.50 – -782.06	<0.001
Köln-Niederrhein-Münsterland	-956.65	-957.46 – -955.83	<0.001
Lüneburger Südheide	-1000.61	-1002.13 – -999.08	<0.001
Maifeld-Neuwieder becken	-1088.81	-1090.65 – - 1086.97	<0.001
Mittelfranken	-1041.96	-1042.79 – - 1041.13	<0.001
München	-761.18	-763.31 – -759.06	<0.001
Müritz-Schorfheide	-1182.27	-1183.22 – - 1181.32	<0.001
Nordfriesland	-807.92	-809.16 – -806.69	<0.001
Oberallgäu	83.64	82.20 – 85.08	<0.001
Odenwald-Spessart	-844.93	-845.93 – -843.93	<0.001
Oderbruch	-1191.84	-1192.96 – - 1190.72	<0.001
Pfälzerwald	-904.94	-906.11 – -903.77	<0.001

Prignitz	-1132.59	-1133.54 – - 1131.63	<0.001
Schwarzwald	-346.83	-347.75 – -345.91	<0.001
Solling-Reinhardswald	-837.08	-838.66 – -835.50	<0.001
Soonwald-Taunus	-1056.93	-1058.64 – - 1055.21	<0.001
Stuttgart-Nordbaden	-957.51	-958.39 – -956.63	<0.001
Teltow-Berlin-Barnim	-1185.67	-1186.83 – - 1184.50	<0.001
Thüringer Wald	-737.39	-738.57 – -736.21	<0.001
Uckermark	-1205.24	-1206.49 – - 1203.98	<0.001
Untere Oder	-1216.68	-1218.44 – - 1214.92	<0.001
Vorderpfalz-Rhein-Main	-1102.91	-1103.82 – - 1102.00	<0.001
Warnow-Vorpommern	-1123.15	-1124.03 – - 1122.28	<0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	13453.30		
τ_{00} Land_Type	139.21		

ICC	0.01
N _{Land_Type}	3
Observations	5331973
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.853 / 0.855

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